

N-Hydroxy-N,N'-Diphenylbenzamidine—A New Type of Analytical Reagent. Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V)

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A method is developed for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) using N-hydroxy-N, N'-diphenylbenzamidine as a new type of reagent. The procedure is selective and most of the common ions including Fe³⁺, Mo⁶⁺, Mn²⁺ and Cr³⁺ do not interfere. Vanadium in BCS steels is determined precisely and accurately.

A method is presented for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) using N-hydroxy-N,N'-diphenylbenzamidine, containing a new type of functional grouping, I. The reagent has

great potentialities for the analytical determination of metal ions^{1,2}. N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diphenylbenzamidine yields water insoluble blue-violet precipitate with vanadate ions in 1.0 to 10.0M acetic acid media which is quantitatively extracted in chloroform to form a blue-violet solution. The complex is extracted instantaneously in about a minute and the coloured system is stable for several days.

The absorbance curve of the coloured system shows a broad absorbance maxima at 550-575 nm when measured against a chloroform blank. The reagent (λ_{max} 315 nm) and the vanadium complex have well separated absorption maxima so that the excess of the reagent does not interfere in the photometric determinations. Final determination of vanadium is based on the measurement of the absorbance of the blue-violet extract at 560 nm. The sensitivity of the reaction as defined by Sandell is 0.011 μg of vanadium per cm^2 at the maximum absorption. The coloured system conformed to Beer's law and the optimum range for colour measurement as computed by Sandell's method is 2.4 to 8.8 ppm of vanadium.

The molar absorptivity of the colour reaction is 4.21×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

The method provides a simple and efficient means for the separation and determination of vanadium in presence of several diverse ions. The common ions including large amounts of Fe³⁺, Cr³⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, molybdate, borate, fluoride, sulphate and nitrate did not interfere with the determination. Titanium and tungstate inhibit the colour development and thus interfere seriously. The merit of the method is that both iron and molybdenum which are commonly associated with vanadium in steels do not interfere. The method demands no rigid control of conditions such as acidity, volume of aqueous phase, temperature and order of mixing the reagents.

Experimental

N-Hydroxy-N,N'-diphenylbenzamidine: The reagent, II, is prepared by the condensation of N-phenylbenzimidoyl chloride and N-phenyl-hydroxylamine in absolute ether medium^{1,2}.

Reagent solution: A 0.1 per cent w/v (0.003M) solution of the reagent in chloroform was employed.

Ammonium metavanadate: A stock solution of ammonium metavanadate containing approximately 0.006 to 0.03 mg of vanadium per ml was prepared

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by dissolving A.R. grade (Hopkin and Williams) substance in double distilled water. Vanadium content of the solution was determined volumetrically using potassium permanganate solution⁸.

Apparatus : Carl Zeiss (Jena) Universal Spectrophotometer VSU I with matched silica cells of 1 cm optical path was employed for all photometric measurements.

Colour reaction : An 1.0–10.0M acetic acid solution of N-hydroxy-N,N'-diphenylbenzamidine reacts with vanadate ions and yields blue-violet precipitate. The precipitate is readily soluble in chloroform. The colour of the chloroform extract is blue-violet. The absorbance curve of the coloured complex showed a broad absorbance maxima at 5505–75 nm when measured against a chloroform blank.

Recommended procedure : It should be ensured that all vanadium ions are in their highest oxidation states. The sample solution is, therefore, treated with a few drops of bromine water, the excess of which is removed by boiling.

To 10 ml aliquot of the solution containing 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of vanadium(V) in a separatory funnel, add 8.6 ml of glacial acetic acid and dilute with distilled water to 25 ml. Add 6 ml 0.1 per cent reagent solution, shaking vigorously for 1 min; then let stand for separation of phases.

Transfer the organic phase to a 50 ml beaker. Wash the aqueous phase with 2 five ml portions of chloroform and add the washings to the contents of the beaker. Dry the combined extracts with 2 g of anhydrous sodium sulphate. Decant the violet solution from the beaker into a 25 ml volumetric flask and washout the adhering colour from the sodium sulphate crystals with small portions of chloroform. Mix the washings with the main solution and dilute to volume. Measure the absorbance at 560 nm in a 1 cm cell against chloroform as blank. As the appropriate blank of the reagent solution in chloroform has practically no absorbance at 560 nm, it can be replaced by chloroform.

Solvents for extraction of blue-violet complex : Of the several organic solvents, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and benzene were found to extract the blue-violet complex from the aqueous phase. Chloroform was preferred because the reagent is more freely soluble in it than in other solvents and with it the quantitative extraction of the coloured complex is readily accomplished.

Results and Discussion

The influence of the following variables on the development of colour was studied.

Acidity : If the concentration of the acetic acid in aqueous phase lies between 1.0 to 10.0M, the wavelength of maximum absorption and the absorbance value of the chloroform extracts remain unchanged. Acidity beyond 10.0M acetic acid is not suitable for extraction work because of the formation of turbidity in the chloroform solution. An

intermediate concentration of 6M was selected for the present work.

Time : The coloured system is stable for atleast 60 hr and the measurement of colour is unaffected by variation in temperature of the aqueous phase from 25° to 40°.

Lambert-Beer law : Concentrations of vanadium (V) from 0.8 and 12 ppm at 560 nm conformed to Lambert-Beer law. Sandell⁴ recommends an optimum range of 0.2 to 0.7 unit for absorbance measurements and hence the practical range for the determination of vanadium by this method is 2.4 to 8.8 ppm of the metal.

Amount of reagent : To ensure the maximum colour development a 1 to 10 molar ratio of vanadium to reagent should be employed. A chloroform

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of (A) Blue-violet complex of Vanadium(V)-Reagent (Vanadium concentration, 100 $\mu\text{g}/25$ ml), (B) Reagent in chloroform (0.1%).

solution of the reagent has its absorption maximum at 315 nm and hence an excess of the reagent has no influence on the measurement of blue-violet colour at 560 nm. In practice for every 0.1 mg of vanadium 6 mg of the reagent has been used throughout the extraction work.

Influence of foreign ions : The effect of foreign ions was studied at 6M acid concentration of the aqueous phase. Varying amounts of the foreign ions were taken with a fixed amount of vanadium, and the colour was developed and measured following the procedure described earlier. Iron(III) reacts with the reagent giving a violet colour if the concentration of the acid in aqueous phase is less than 4M, thus interfering seriously with the determination of vanadium. The interference was eliminated by maintaining the acidity between 4.0 and 10.0M. Titanium, zirconium and tungstate inhibit the colour development and thus seriously interfere. The use of the common masking agents⁵ to eliminate the interference of these ions was not successful. Molybdenum (VI) reacts with the reagent throughout the acidity forming a chloroform soluble light yellow extract, but its colour does not interfere with measurement of the vanadium complex at 560 nm. The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Vanadium concentration, 100 µg/25 ml
Acetic acid concentration of the aqueous phase, 6M

Ions	Added as	Amount added ppm	Absorbance, 560 nm
—	—	—	0.33
Fe ³⁺	Fe(NO ₃) ₃	800	0.33
Cr ³⁺	K ₂ SO ₄ .Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃ .24H ₂ O	350	0.33
Al ³⁺	Al(NO ₃) ₃	400	0.33
Co ²⁺	Co(NO ₃) ₂	400	0.33
Ni ²⁺	Ni(NO ₃) ₂	400	0.33
UO ₂ ²⁺	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	250	0.33
Ce ⁴⁺	2(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ .Ce(SO ₄) ₂ .24H ₂ O	300	0.33
Zn ²⁺	Zn(NO ₃) ₂	400	0.33
Mn ²⁺	MnSO ₄ .4H ₂ O	400	0.33
Cu ²⁺	CuSO ₄ .5H ₂ O	420	0.33
Sb ³⁺	C ₄ H ₄ O ₆ K(SbO)	400	0.33
Tl ³⁺	Tl ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	400	0.33
MoO ₄ ²⁻	(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ .4H ₂ O	350	0.335
AsO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₂ H.AsO ₄ .7H ₂ O	800	0.33
F ⁻	NaF	250	0.33
PO ₄ ³⁻	Na ₃ PO ₄	400	0.33
B ₄ O ₇ ²⁻	Na ₂ B ₄ O ₇ .10H ₂ O	220	0.33
SO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ SO ₄	440	0.33
Cl ⁻	NaCl	500	0.33
NO ₃ ⁻	NaNO ₃	400	0.33
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄ .2H ₂ O	80	0.22
Ti ⁴⁺	K ₂ TiO(C ₂ O ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O	20	0.305
Zr ⁴⁺	Zr(SO ₄) ₂ .4H ₂ O	20	0.30

*Determination of vanadium in steels*²: The method was tried on British Chemical Standards Samples. Two tungsten-vanadium steels, 64a and 241/1 containing 5.66 and 19.61 per cent of tungsten respectively and a tungsten-free low alloy steel, 252 were selected for the purpose. Table 2 shows that the results obtained are in excellent agreement with the certified values.

Procedure: Dissolve a weighed quantity of the steel containing 2.5 mg of vanadium in 40 per cent nitric acid. Since tungsten interferes seriously it

must be removed as hydrated tungstic oxide before vanadium is finally determined. Filter through a Whatman No. 540 filter paper and wash the beaker several times with hot water. Collect the filtrate

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM IN BCS* STEELS

BCS steel	Vanadium found %	Certified value %	<i>s</i>
64a	1.546; 1.55; 1.538;		
Alloy steel	1.56; 1.556	1.57	0.0084
	Average value, 1.55		
241/1	1.560; 1.556; 1.536;		
High speed steel	1.528; 1.556; 1.540	1.57	0.0130
	Average value, 1.546		
252	0.440; 0.460; 0.450;		
Low alloy steel	0.450; 0.455	0.46	0.0074
	Average value, 0.451		

* BCS—British Chemical Standards, Bureau of Analyzed Samples, Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, Yorks.

in a 250 ml beaker, evaporate to near dryness and dilute with water. Transfer to a 250 ml volumetric flask and make up the volume. Determine vanadium from this solution using the recommended procedure.

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